

MODERN METHODS AND TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Radjabova Jayron Ikram qizi

EFL teacher of English Department at Tashkent State University
of Uzbek Language and Literature

radjabovajayron99@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The article substantiates the importance of teaching foreign students the Russian language using the case study method. Now it is said that it is necessary to strengthen the communication component when teaching English as a foreign language. This goal can be facilitated by the use of cases in classes with foreigners. Classic case promotes the development of skills for making independent decisions, the goal working with a case in a classroom with foreigners, another – communicative workshop The article lists topics on which foreigners can offer cases, and the development of one of the cases is presented as a sample the concept we propose.

Key words: case study, English as a foreign language, communication, interactive teaching methods.

The case study method is a method of active analysis of a problem situation, based on learning by solving specific situational problems. The essence of the case study method: students, divided into groups, must analyze the situation and develop a practical solution; end of the process - evaluation of the proposed algorithms and discussion of them within general discussion in the context of the problem posed. We offer case studies in the classical sense, where in the case presents a life problem situation that students need to decide based on existing knowledge, practical experience and intuition.

Since any situation has several possible solutions, there is a discussion of all possible solutions. The use of case studies is limited in lessons of English as a native language, since the features of the material (spelling and punctuation, grammar and phonetics) suggest when solving a problem situation, usually there is one correct answer. But when teaching English as a foreign language, case studies can be used quite widely. When solving a problematic case problem, listening skills develop, take into account an alternative point of view and express your own, navigate and adapt to a new language environment for foreigners, remain face to face with real situations.

With this method you quickly adaptable foreign students have the opportunity be ready to work in a team, find the most rational solution to the task. Analytical and communication skills, research activities are carried out. It is natural to use situational analysis both for teaching professional and everyday communication. When choosing a topic, an individual approach and what is relevant is important for this group of students. It is necessary to focus on the characteristics of a given team: age, country, nationality. Information is selected that is relevant and acceptable for this specific group of students, taking into account national traditions and mentality. It is important to determine the nature of the relationship between the participants. How often do they communicate with each other? What emotional climate formed between them?

To improve the quality of education in our country, a teacher must, first of all, create and try to maintain a favorable classroom climate. Rules such as creating a favorable climate, taking into account psychological characteristics of each child in the class, as well as a clear demonstration of learning goals, are fundamental to the educational process. This style helps to achieve excellence in teaching and learning, however, by constantly maintaining discipline.

A pedagogical requirement is very often expressed with a threat, through an unfriendly tone. Here on discipline, more thorough is done emphasis than on student learning. Moreover, this style is also requires a certain professionalism from the teacher. The disadvantages of the authoritarian style are that its excessive use can harm the student, especially the younger student, as children develop frustration, distrust of adults, as well as peers, often completely unsociability. The most effective teaching style is the democratic style. Basically, it is this style that is practiced in teaching, in present time. The emphasis here is on the motivation of the child, the effective and fruitful work of the entire team. Unlike authoritarian style, the psychological state of the child during training, here, not suffers. And in comparison with the liberal style, discipline does not collapse. The democratic style is the most often implemented, since by correctly implementing it, the teacher is able to achieve the most desired results. In this case, a combination of traditional and interactive methods can give good results both in the application of knowledge and practical skills, and in the formation of a scale of moral values among students, which is an important factor in raising a harmonious personality and improving interethnic relations. During testing on our intercultural communication was valuable - this is verbal and non-verbal communication between speakers of different languages and cultures. Important for this article will be a brief description of the psychological characteristics of children of middle school age.

In total, it is worth noting that the transition from the junior stage of education to the middle stage, that is, in the 5th grade, it is characterized by numerous changes, both

in the child's behavior in society and in his character. And this is not surprising, so as an approach to teaching in primary schools, is very different from approach in high school. The educational process can take place through the implementation of additional resources for learning.

Schoolchildren of this age period are also distinguished by the fact that it is difficult for them keep attention on one thing. Thus, it is advisable for the teacher to try in every possible way to diversify the educational process, use creative approaches and methods in teaching, even if the principle of clarity is implemented in textbooks. All those creative aspects of teaching will be welcomed schoolchildren, which will help the teacher find a common language with them and create a favorable atmosphere in the classroom for subsequent fruitful work. Currently, the role of active teaching methods is increasing in the process of preparing future managers for intercultural interaction, since passive teaching methods are ineffective in the development of sustainable knowledge, abilities, skills and professional competencies of students during the educational process. Memorizing lecture materials and textbook content does not provide a practical component, and thus, students acquire theoretical knowledge without being able to apply it in practice in real life. Unlike passive, active teaching methods promote independent knowledge of the world by students during activities in class and outside of class time. Thus, having worked through a number of problem situations and specific ways to solve them using active learning methods, in the future, future specialists learn to creatively approach the assigned tasks and independently search for non-standard solutions that are most effective in each specific case. All this is especially relevant in connection with constant growth of demands on managers as specialists capable of understanding and accepting the cultural diversity of the modern world. First, let's look at what active methods are. In recent years, in the process of teaching a foreign language.

A successful educational process in the field of a foreign language is well-organized independent work of students. Productive independent work of students becomes important when teaching a foreign language. The role of the teacher is to correctly direct the cognitive activity of students, which they perform independently. Analysis of scientific sources on content and organization the process of teaching a foreign language in universities confirms the axiomatic position that independent work is an invariant structural version of a single teaching foreign language complex. The main task of any university is to prepare specialists for independent practical activities.

Independent work is a type of educational activity performed by students in the classroom, both under the guidance of a teacher and without direct guidance from the teacher during self-study and participation in various extracurricular activities. In

recent years, independent work has become a mandatory part of the learning process, which is specially planned and primarily involves individual work by students in accordance with the instructions of the teacher or training program. In modern methodological literature, independent work of students is considered, on the one hand, as a type of educational activity that is carried out without direct participation of the teacher, but under his guidance, and with on the other hand, as a means of involving students in independent cognitive activity. Independent work of students is especially important during training foreign languages, since students are provided with educational materials that need to be memorized, analyzed, consolidated, and this becomes possible only in conditions of independent work. When teaching foreign languages, there are educational materials that can be learned in classroom lessons when working in pairs, in groups, or in the process of individual work of students. How effective independent work of students will be carried out in the classroom and outside it, in primarily depends on the organization of this work by the teacher.

The priority role of the student in independent work does not reduce the role of the teacher, but on the contrary makes his task more complex, increases requirements for him as the organizer of this process. Teacher's task is to correctly direct and organize the cognitive activity of students, which they perform independently. That there is a teacher who needs to create a development situation that provides the student with freedom and responsibility in choice and decision-making, independence of action in solving educational problems, combined with taking responsibility for the result. Based on the fact that linguistic students must master the English language to conduct professional activities, we use a deductive approach to explain new grammatical material.

The use of this approach in teaching grammar involves analyzing the form of the grammatical phenomenon being studied and the ways of its use, and also requires knowledge of grammatical rules. In order to master the form of a grammatical phenomenon using the deductive method of explaining grammar, we use training, analytical exercise character, as well as tests and tasks testing knowledge of grammatical rules. Using interactive teaching of practical English grammar, we strive to organize the learning process in such a way that so that all students are involved in the process of learning English grammar and have the opportunity to reflect on what they are studying grammatical phenomenon. By organizing joint activities of students to master grammatical material, we strive to ensure opportunity for students to exchange knowledge, ideas, methods activities. When the groups have completed the assigned exercises, a frontal check is carried out. From each group one student is asked, usually a weak one. If students not only demonstrate correct completion of tasks, but

are also able to answer additional questions, the teacher evaluates the group's work, assigning one mark per the whole group. If students make mistakes when answering, the student the grammatical material is explained by the teacher again. The concept of information-cognitive competence is closely related with the concept of cognitive competence. Cognitive competence represents a set of knowledge and skills to carry out independent cognitive activity. Information and cognitive competence is the ability of students to search for necessary information and analyze it using information and communication technologies. Due to the development of information technology nowadays

The approach to organizing the process of teaching a foreign language in higher education has changed significantly. Visual aids based on multimedia technologies are widely used, making it possible to carry out the learning process at a qualitatively new level. One of the most popular today are multimedia presentations. Presentations can be used as support for listening, retelling texts, composing dialogues. Such the wide range of applications of multimedia presentations is explained by because presentations "bring variety, enliven the learning process, increase the emotional impact on students, create a comfortable learning environment, and help form a model of real communication". It is also important that the development of presentations increases the information culture of students, their motivation and self-esteem. With the help of the presentation, the student has the ability to structure your speech logically and coherently, express your thoughts sufficiently fully and correctly in linguistic terms.

When organizing a lesson using a presentation, educational material is presented clearly and more accessible than if it were in ordinary oral form. During his speech, the student has the opportunity to use keywords, diagrams, tables, pictures that he has prepared. This allows you to speak consistently, comprehensively, and confidently and expressively. Topic presentations can be used effectively as an assessment tool. Students are tasked with presenting a speech on an oral topic accompanied by a multimedia presentation. Having studied the lexical and grammatical material on the proposed topic, they must independently compose oral messages, select illustrative material, and present their messages to the audience.

REFERENCES

1. Brown H. Principles of Language Learning and Teaching. Prentice Hall, 1994
2. Cook, V. Linguistics and Second Language Acquisition. London: Macmillan: 1993.
3. Hinkel, E. Current perspectives on teaching the four skills. *Tesol Quarterly*, 40(1), 2006.
4. Khasanova Maftuna Sherali kizi. (2023) Teaching English Grammar using Interactive Methods. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd)*, Special Issue | Modern Trends in Science, Technology and Economy, 402-403, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd56307.pdf>
5. M. Sh. Khasanova, N. B. Mirzayeva. Importance of CLT in teaching vocabulary to adult learners. *E3S Web of Conf.* 413 03017 (2023). DOI: 10.1051/e3sconf/202341303017
6. Nasiba Mirzayeva Bakhtiyar kizi. (2023). The Importance of Communicative Approach in Acquiring a Second Language. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 3(4), 36–42. Retrieved from <https://openaccessjournals.eu/index.php/jedic/article/view/2050>